

Species Coexistence as an Emergent Effect of Interacting Mechanisms

Supplementary Material

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Supplementary Material Content

The supplementary material for our paper is structured as follows: This document firstly contains additional explanations for the proposed model, particularly implementation details and pseudocode, to complement the conceptual overview presented in the paper itself. Second, the document presents and discusses the results of the validation experiments for demographic stochasticity, storage effect, and intransitivity, for which we compare our model against those presented by Danino et al. (2016) and Laird and Schamp (2006).

In addition to this document, we provide the full, annotated source code from which we generated all our data, as well as the obtained data itself and all files that were used for plotting the results. The code is written in pure, simple, modern C++ and is almost entirely self-contained. OpenMP is the only dependency outside the C++ standard library and was used for speeding up experiments. Although the models themselves are almost entirely platform-agnostic, we programmed for a Linux environment as far as file inputs and outputs are concerned. For plotting, we used Matlab and hence provide Matlab scripts.

1. Implementation of the Multi-Mechanism Model

In this section, we show how the explained concept of the multi-mechanism model was implemented by us. We provide function definitions, pseudocode for important simulation parts and in depth descriptions where appropriate. At first, a high level overview of the program flow is given, then we go into the details of individual parts. To better understand these explanations in the overall context, meaning when and where they come into play, please refer to the conceptual overview given in the paper.

1.1. Program Flow

The model is initialized with a simulation area of a certain size, a number of species, a number of resources, their respective initial abundances, etc. The Table 4 gives an overview of the model parameters. After initialization, the simulation is run in a loop until the abundance of a species drops to zero (until the first extinction event). It also terminates if no extinction occurs within a certain number of generations.

```
1: // The updating loop of the program
2: repeat
3:     // Phase 1: Planning
4:     for all individuals do
5:         plan the next action;
6:     end for
7:
8:     // Phase 2: Acting
9:     for all individuals do
10:        act according to plan;
11:    end for
12:
13:    // Phase 3: Resolving
14:    for all individuals do
15:        resolve time step;
16:    end for
17:    execute birth events;
18:    execute death events;
19:    update environmental fluctuations;
20: until a species goes extinct
```

Each iteration of the simulation consists of three phases: planning, acting, and resolving. In the planning phase, each simulated individual determines its next goal and reports back how much time it would take to achieve said goal. The simulation then advances by the shortest amount of reported time during the acting phase, where all individuals advance towards their respective goals, constrained by how much time they have been given. Finally, in the resolving phase achieved goals are translated to consequences, death chances are evaluated, population abundances adjusted and environmental fluctuations updated. Then the loop begins anew, unless the termination criteria was met.

```
1: // The planning phase for a single individual
2: if in searching state then
3:     if no target is selected then
4:         select target;
5:     end if
6:     return time needed to reach target;
7: else if in pickup state then
8:     return time needed to finish pickup;
9: end if
```

Fundamentally, individuals are always in one of two states: Either they are searching for resources, or they are already in the process of picking up a resource. If the individual is searching, a target needs to be chosen first, unless one is chosen already. Then, the amount of time it would take to move towards the resource, such that it can be picked up, is calculated and returned. If the individual is already in the process of picking up a resource, it simply needs to return the amount of time left until the pickup is complete.

```
1: // The acting phase for a single individual
2: if in searching state then
3:     move towards resource;
4:     if resource is within interaction radius then
5:         enter state "in pickup state";
6:     end if
7: else if in pickup state then
8:     reduce pickup countdown;
9: end if
```

Once each individual has planned its goal and reported back, the simulation

advances by the shortest reported required time during the acting phase. Now the individuals advance towards their goals according to how much time they have been given. If the individual is searching, it will move closer to its chosen resource. If the resource is then within the interaction radius, the individual will enter the pickup state. Otherwise, if the individual is in the pickup state, it simply reduces the countdown towards completing the pickup by the given time.

```
1: // The resolving phase
2: for all individuals do
3:     if in pickup state then
4:         if pickup countdown completed then
5:             if there are competitors then
6:                 trigger competition event for pickup;
7:             else
8:                 pickup the resource;
9:             end if
10:            enter state "in searching state";
11:        end if
12:    end if
13:    if survival check fails then
14:        mark individual as dead;
15:    end if
16: end for
17:
18: execute birth events;
19: execute death events;
20: update environmental fluctuations;
```

In the final phase, the results of this iteration are determined and processed. For each individual, there are two steps involved: 1) If the individual is picking up a resource, and if the pickup countdown was completed, then a competition is triggered in case that there are competitors for the resource, otherwise the resource is picked up directly. The individual enters the searching state afterwards. 2) The individual undergoes a survival check. If the check fails, the individual is marked as dead. After these two steps are done for each individual, a birth event is triggered for each individual and for each resource marked as dead. Then, the marked individuals and resources are removed from the simulation. Finally, the environmental fluctuations are updated,

thereby altering the effective fitness of the species. This concludes the high level overview of the program flow. Next we will look into the details of the functions we used.

1.2. Function for Target Selection

During planning, individuals in the searching state may need to select a resource as target before they can proceed. The most straightforward solution would be to always choose the closest resource. However, this implies perfect perception, which is unrealistic. Additionally, individuals which are close to each other will choose the same resources. We observed a very strong converging effect in preliminary experiments with this method, where eventually individuals would form very dense clusters and move in sync. The method we eventually implemented solves these issues.

```
1: // Function for target selection
2: initialize empty list of resource candidates;
3: for all resource species do
4:     get the 5 closest resources of this species;
5:     calculate the squared distances towards them;
6:     invert these squared distances;
7:     select a random resource from among the 5, using the inverses as
        weights;
8:     add the selected resource to the list of resource candidates;
9: end for
10: calculate the distances towards all resource candidates;
11: Multiply the distances by the inverse of the applicable preference;
12: Select the candidate with the smallest distance as target;
```

It works as follows: First, we select a representative candidate from each resource species. This candidate is randomly chosen from among the 5 closest members of the species, where the likelihood to be chosen is inversely proportional to the squared distance from the choosing individual. Consequently, closer resources are significantly more likely to become a representative candidate. The number 5 was determined through preliminary experimentation. It was found to reliably prevent the clustering problem we described, and there was no need to change it further. Once a candidate for each resource species is determined, we deterministically select from among those the one which is perceived to be closest. For this, we take the corresponding resource

preferences into account by multiplying the real distances with the inverses of these preferences.

1.3. *Handling of Movement and Pickups*

Movement is modeled completely linearly, meaning that individuals always move in straight lines and with a constant speed. The speed per time step is calculated as $base\ speed \times fitness$. The base speed is a constant, but the fitness changes according to the environmental fluctuations. Only individuals in the searching state are moving, and their movement is always towards their selected resource. Once an individual has reached the resource, such that it is within the interaction radius, the individual shifts to the pickup state. When entering this state, a countdown is initialized. The time to complete the countdown is set equal to the time it would take the individual to move to the position of the resource. It follows that the required time increases proportionally with the size of the interaction radius, and inversely proportional with the speed of the individual. The pickup countdown is reduced in the acting phases as time progresses. Once the countdown reaches 0, the individual picks up the resource if it is the only competitor for it. Otherwise, a competition with all competitors over the resource is triggered. When picking up a resource, it is marked as dead, and the individual has its storage counter increased by one. If the storage counter cannot be increased further, the time since last consumption is reset to 0 for the individual.

1.4. *Handling of Competitions*

A competition occurs when multiple individuals are in the pickup process for the same resources, and when the pickup countdown for any one of them has reached 0. The competition consists of a series of pairwise tournaments. The participants of each tournament are chosen randomly. The winner of a tournament is the individual with the higher fitness. When comparing the fitness, the pairwise competitive relation between the involved species is taken into account. This is done by applying the corresponding fitness multiplier, as defined by the relation, to one of the competitors. Example: If the competitive relation from A to B is defined as 2, then either the fitness of A is multiplied by 2, or the fitness of B is multiplied by $1/2$, but not both. The loser of each tournament is eliminated from the competition. Eventually, only one competitor remains, who gets to pick up the resource. There is no penalty for losing in a competition, except for missing out on the resource.

1.5. Handling of Survival Checks

All individuals undergo a survival check in the resolving phase. Since time steps can represent varying amounts of time, the survival check needs to account for this: The time step is divided into full-second intervals, and a final fractional interval. Then the survival chances for each interval are computed and aggregated. Finally, it is determined whether the individual survives or not.

```
1: // Handling of survival checks
2: initialize cumulative survival chance with value 1
3: divide time step into intervals
4: for all intervals do
5:     evaluate mortality rate function for the start time of this interval
6:     convert obtained death chance per second into survival chance per
       second
7:     if survival chance < confidence threshold then
8:         if there is food in storage then
9:             eat food
10:            reevaluate this interval
11:        end if
12:    end if
13:    if interval is fractional then
14:        take survival chance to the power of the interval length
15:    end if
16:    multiply survival chance into the cumulative survival chance
17: end for
18: Generate random number from 0 to 1
19: if random number > cumulative survival chance then
20:     Mark individual as dead
21: end if
```

For each interval, the mortality rate function is evaluated. As input for this function, we use the time since the last resource consumption as of the beginning of the current interval of the time step. From this we obtain a death chance per second. For the next steps, we translate this into a logically equivalent survival chance per second. The survival chance is compared to a confidence threshold, which we define as follows: $1 - (1/\textit{mortality span})$, where mortality span is a parameter of the mortality rate function. If the survival chance of this interval is below the threshold, the individual will

consume a stored resource (if possible) and the interval is reevaluated. On reevaluation, the survival chance becomes maximal, as the time since last consumption is then 0. In the following intervals, the chances begin to drop again. Once the survival chance per second for this interval is fixed, it may need to be adjusted in the case that the interval is fractional. In this case, the survival chance per second is taken to the power of the length of the fractional interval: $survival\ chance^{interval\ length}$. Then, the obtained survival chance is multiplied into the cumulative survival chance for the time step. Finally, a random value between 0 and 1 is computed and compared against the cumulative survival chance. If the check fails, the individual is marked as dead.

1.6. Function for the Mortality Rate

The mortality rate function maps the time since last resource consumption onto a death chance per second. We use a simple bounded reciprocal function to model this relationship between starvation and mortality. The function is defined by two parameters: mortality span and mortality index. It always intersects the points $(0, 0)$ and $(mortality\ span, 1)$. Therefore, the mortality span corresponds to the longest theoretically achievable time for an individual to survive without consuming resources. The mortality index describes the curvature of the function. For very large values, the function becomes approximately linear. For small values, a smooth curve with monotonously increasing upwards slope is obtained.

$$death\ chance\ per\ second = \frac{i}{s + i - t} - \frac{i(s - t)}{(s + i)s}$$

For brevity, we abbreviated mortality span to s , mortality index to i and the time since last resource consumption to t in the above equation.

1.7. Execution of birth and death events

Our simulation is zero-sum based. In our case, this means that the total amount of individuals, and the total amount of available resources per resource species are constant. Therefore, each death event must be compensated by a birth event. During the initial part of the resolving phase, individuals and resources are marked as dead, but not yet removed. In the later stage of the resolving phase, first each death is compensated by a birth. Individuals are of a random species, weighted according to the abundance multiplied by the fitness of each species. For this step, Individuals marked as dead are still

counted to the abundance of each species, but the newly birthed individuals are not. Resources are always of the same species as the resource which they are replacing. New individuals and resources start at random positions within the simulation area.

1.8. Function for Environmental Fluctuations

The environmental fluctuations assign fitness multipliers to species. The assigned multipliers can change at the end of each time step. This models the varying species responses to an ever-changing environment. We consider two different approaches, both characterized by the same two parameters: environmental fluctuation amplitude and environmental persistence time (shortened to amplitude and persistence time in the following). The amplitude is defined as the ratio between the highest possible fitness multiplier and the lowest, while the persistence time is given in seconds and determines how frequently the environment changes. Both parameters are ≥ 1 . Based on the amplitude, the minimum and maximum multipliers are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{max multiplier} &= \sqrt{1 + \text{amplitude}} \\ \text{min multiplier} &= \frac{1}{\text{max multiplier}} \end{aligned}$$

To obtain the chance per second that the environment changes, the inverse of the persistence time is taken. As time steps can represent varying amounts of time, we take this change chance per second and take it to the power of the time represented by the time step:

$$\text{change chance} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\text{persistence time}} \right)^{\text{time span}}$$

With the minimum and maximum multipliers, as well as the change chance calculated, we can now describe how the two different approaches use them. We call the first approach correlated dichotomous noise. It was proposed by Danino et al. (2016), and we use it to compare our model with theirs. The approach is simple and works only for two-species scenarios. The simulation is initialized with one of the species having the maximum multiplier and the other having the minimum multiplier. Then, whenever the environment changes, the multipliers are swapped between the species. As this approach cannot handle multi-species scenarios, we added a variation of it, which we call independent multilevel noise. In this case, we assign a random positive

multiplier between 1 and the maximum, or a random negative multiplier between 1 and the minimum for each species independently. The chances to get a positive or negative outcome are equal. When the environment changes, the multipliers are randomly assigned anew. This method supports any number of species and allows for intermediate fitness multipliers, which is important for our multi-mechanism scenarios.

2. Validation Experiments

In this section, we present and discuss experiments that compare individual aspects of our model against the established literature. We selected models for comparison that integrate coexistence mechanisms on top of fundamentally neutral dynamics (all species being functionally equal), which is similar to our model. We chose parameter settings (Table 4) such that the models are as close to being equivalent as possible. Some parameters only apply to our model, in which case we settled upon sensible values during preliminary experiments. Some statistics helped us with this, particularly the average competition ratio (likelihood that competitions occur) and the average time to resources (average time to collect a resource). All validation experiments have a competition ratio of about 40% and a time to resources of about 10. An exception is the intransitivity experiment, which has values of about 70% and 15 respectively, which was necessary to speed up calculations for this very large scenario (increased mortality leads to shorter lifespans and fewer calculations per generation).

The validation experiments show that the multi-mechanism model successfully captures the behavior of basic neutral dynamics, storage effect, and intransitivity. Naturally, there are some deviations in the details, which is to be expected considering that our model is more general and functionally different.

Neutral Dynamics & Storage Effect

For basic neutral dynamics and storage effect, we compare against models presented in Danino et al. (2016). In their paper, a basic neutral model with pure demographic stochasticity (drift) is described in Section III. This basic model is then extended to include the storage effect in Section V. We implemented their models as a reference for ours. Note that the environmental persistence time is given in generations for the reference model, while it is given in seconds in our model. A value of 0.2 for the reference model translates into

Figure 1: Comparison of our model in terms of neutral dynamics and storage effect with a reference model.

a $1/20$ chance of the environment to change for each elementary simulation step (a single birth and death) for a total population size of 100. A value of 20 for our model translates into a $1/20$ chance for the environment to change per second of simulation. Since generations can span varying amounts of time in our model, no exactly equivalent mapping of this parameter is possible. For storage effect, we use a max. stored food parameter of 1 in our model, which corresponds to the lower boundary of representable levels of storage. The results are shown by Figure 1 and presented in the same form as in the reference paper. In each case, we analyze the stability of a two-species scenario based on differing relative starting abundances. The abundance ratios are denoted by the x-axis, while the y-axis corresponds to the average time of coexistence in generations for that respective initial ratio. As we can see, the results are within a few generations of the reference. Notably, our validation experiment for the storage effect used the weakest possible strength of the mechanism that our model allows for. This seems to suggest that our implementation of this effect has more potential upside than the variant presented by Danino et al. (2016).

Beyond the comparison with Danino et al. (2016), we further investigate the behavior of our model at various degrees of storage. Here, we are particularly interested in whether all three formal requirements for the storage effect are met: covariance between competition and environment, differing

Table 1: Competition frequency as measured by number of competitions experienced per time unit per individual. Advantaged is abbreviated to Adv. and Disadvantaged to Disadv.

Max. Storage	<i>Relative Species Abundances</i>		
	Adv. < 10% Disadv. \geq 90%	Adv. 45%–55% Disadv. 45%–55%	Adv. \geq 90% Disadv. < 10%
0	0.05610	0.06327	0.07160
1	0.05594	0.06360	0.07152
4	0.05612	0.06338	0.07165
16	0.05612	0.06338	0.07146

species fitness responses to the same environments, and the ability of rare species to persist through periods of competitive disadvantage until favorable conditions return. The second requirement is trivial to infer from the model structure, but the first and third require verification. To this end, we use the same experiment as above for storage effect validation, but always with equal starting abundances, and 100 repetitions each for 0, 1, 4, and 16 storage. The obtained persistence times were 61, 99, 190, and 206 generations, respectively. By logging detailed statistics for each species per experienced environment, we can quantify competition frequency, competition intensity, and mortality. We group the statistics based on species abundances and fitnesses, such that we can observe how measurements change in relation to environments and densities. This two-species scenario uses correlated dichotomous noise for environmental fluctuations, which is ideal for filtering out the effects we want to observe. It guarantees that environments change in sync for both species, hence, whenever the abundant species is advantaged, the rare species is certainly disadvantaged and vice versa. Additionally, the two fitness values between which the species fluctuate are known and constant, thus creating a rather controlled testbed.

To check for covariance between environment and competition, we first look at Table 1, which lists the average number of competitions experienced across all individuals per time step. Consistent with expectations, the measurements clearly indicate that competition frequency is highest when the advantaged species is most abundant and lowest in the opposite case. This trend is virtually identical in magnitude and distribution regardless of storage capabilities. As Table 2 reveals, this also translates into increased competition intensity for both species, as measured by the number of resources collected per individual per time unit. In this case, we also split the measurement into

Table 2: Competition intensity as measured by resources collected per time unit per individual. Advantaged is abbreviated to Adv. and Disadvantaged to Disadv.

Max. Storage	<i>Relative Species Abundances</i>		
	Adv. < 10% Disadv. \geq 90%	Adv. 45%–55% Disadv. 45%–55%	Adv. \geq 90% Disadv. < 10%
<i>Resource collection ability of the advantaged species</i>			
0	0.11442	0.10572	0.09217
1	0.11389	0.10668	0.09252
4	0.11390	0.10671	0.09306
16	0.11314	0.10579	0.09186
<i>Resource collection ability of the disadvantaged species</i>			
0	0.06999	0.05929	0.05310
1	0.07014	0.05910	0.05341
4	0.06964	0.05903	0.05171
16	0.06899	0.05856	0.05136

the impact of increased competition on the advantaged species and the disadvantaged species. As expected, environmentally disadvantaged species are consistently less capable of competing for resources as opposed to advantaged species. Additionally, we observe a clear correlation between the abundance of the advantaged species and the increasing competitive pressure this exerts on the whole system. As before, the trend we observe barely changes with different levels of storage and remains consistent throughout all setups. To check for the ability of rare species to persist throughout unfavorable conditions, we look at Table 3, which quantifies mortality as measured by the death chances per individual per time step. We distinguish between the mortality in favorable and hostile environments and are particularly interested in the case of low to very low abundance of the rare species. As the model is zero-sum based, relative differences between the species are especially important, and are hence highlighted in the third block of the table. Evidently, the presence of storage capabilities has a very clear impact on individual mortality. As per the formal requirement, higher storage increasingly enables disadvantaged species to survive adverse environments, and the effect becomes stronger the rarer the disadvantaged species is. Indeed, in the strongest case of abundance lower than 5% and 16 storage, mortality of the disadvantaged species sinks well below that of the advantaged. Notably, the effect also aids advantaged species when they are rare, as seen in the case where they have less than 10%

Table 3: Mortality as measured by death chances per time unit per individual. Advantaged is abbreviated to Adv. and Disadvantaged to Disadv.

Storage	<i>Relative Species Abundances</i>			
	Max. Adv. < 10% Disadv. \geq 90%	Adv. 45%–55% Disadv. 45%–55%	Adv. \geq 90% Disadv. < 10%	Adv. \geq 95% Disadv. < 5%
<i>Mortality of the advantaged species</i>				
0	0.00187	0.00205	0.00201	0.00200
1	0.00151	0.00167	0.00167	0.00167
4	0.00148	0.00165	0.00168	0.00168
16	0.00172	0.00192	0.00194	0.00194
<i>Mortality of the disadvantaged species</i>				
0	0.00209	0.00230	0.00228	0.00222
1	0.00174	0.00186	0.00182	0.00177
4	0.00173	0.00181	0.00176	0.00171
16	0.00198	0.00203	0.00193	0.00185
<i>Relative gap between advantaged and disadvantaged species mortality</i>				
0	11.76%	12.20%	13.43%	11.00%
1	15.23%	11.38%	8.98%	5.99%
4	16.89%	9.70%	4.76%	1.79%
16	15.12%	5.73%	-0.52%	-4.64%

abundance, in which the mortality gap is particularly high, thus helping the rarer species in this case. Nonetheless, the effect is stronger for disadvantaged species. Overall, these results clearly indicate the presence of all three formal requirements for the storage effect in our model.

Finally, the tables show some details that we want to address shortly. First, competition frequency and intensity are not perfect predictors of mortality, even in the absence of storage. This may be because they don't take newborns into account (which start with 0% mortality) or more likely because variance in resource collection and consumption are not accounted for (less frequent but more regular consumption intervals are expected to yield lower mortality than overall more frequent but irregular intervals). Second, we observe that absolute mortality rates decline from 0 storage to 4 storage, but then increase again at 16 storage. We experimentally verified that this is an artifact of our chosen static confidence threshold with which individuals decide when to consume from storage. The threshold works decently for lower amounts of storage, but is not adequate for larger capacities, at least not when resources on average can be picked up more frequently than the consumption from storage triggers. Though the mechanism still functions, an adaptable confidence threshold may

be more sensible, such that individuals more readily eat from storage when they are fit and have ample reserves, while remaining conservative when unfit and with few reserves left.

Intransitivity

Figure 2: Results of our intransitivity validation experiments, showing the evolution of species abundances over time for five different networks of pairwise competitive relations.

To validate the intransitivity mechanism, we compare with the experiment outlined in Laird and Schamp (2006). We use the same five scenarios of various pairwise intransitive relations between six different species as they did, thus replicating the competition matrices shown in their Figure 1. Further, we use the same color codes for each of the species, and our curves are labeled according to the corresponding case (1 to 5) like in the reference. Their Figure 2 shows the surviving individuals in the generations 0, 1, 4, 16, 64, 256, and 500, from which the abundance per species at those generations can be derived. Similarly, our Figure 2 shows the abundance of each species per

generation for our experiment. Although the formats are different, the results are directly comparable in terms of species abundances over time. There are no environmental fluctuations in this experiment, hence competitions between individuals from different species are always deterministically decided. This behavior matches the reference model. Comparing our Figure 2 with their Figure 2, it is evident that the models thoroughly agree on the underlying dynamics. Both models agree on which species go extinct, how fast they go extinct, and at which levels their abundance can stabilize. Extinctions occur roughly around generation 7 in cases 3, 4, and 5 and around generation 20 in cases 1 and 2. In Case 3, it can be observed that both models predict that the red and dark blue species stabilize at higher abundance than the other three surviving species. A deeper comparison could be made by comparing our results with the achieved abundances for each generation in their case. Of particular interest here would be the magnitude of abundance fluctuations as a result of the intransitive loop, which is very visible in case 2 of our plot. This may be investigated by future research on the topic.

References

- Laird, R. A. & Schamp B.S. (2006). Competitive Intransitivity Promotes Species Coexistence. *The American Naturalist*, 168, 182–193.
- Danino, M., Kessler, D. A. & Shnerb, N. M. (2016). Stability of two-species communities: Drift, environmental stochasticity, storage effect and selection. *Theoretical Population Biology*, 119, 57–71.

Table 4: Parameters used in our validation experiments. Parameters of reference models are listed under Ref. (if applicable), while parameters of our model are listed under Ours. Independent Multilevel is abbreviated to Multil., and Correlated Dichotomous to Dicho.

Parameter	<i>Neutral Dynamics</i>		<i>Storage Effect</i>		<i>Intransitivity</i>	
	Ref.	Ours	Ref.	Ours	Ref.	Ours
<i>Parameters of the individuals.</i>						
Active Species	2	2	2	2	6	6
Active Population Size	100	100	100	100	10000	9996
Base Speed	-	0.9	-	0.88	-	11
Interaction Radius	-	3.1	-	3.11	-	19.94
Mortality Span	-	200	-	200	-	200
Mortality Index	-	4	-	4	-	4
<i>Parameters of the environment.</i>						
Resource Species	-	1	-	1	-	1
Resource Population Size	-	161	-	161	-	2507
Simulation Area	-	100	-	100	-	5000
Stochasticity Type	Multil.	Multil.	Dicho.	Dicho.	-	Multil.
E. Fluctuation Amplitude	0	0	0.5	0.5	-	0
E. Persistence Time	0	0	0.2	20	-	0
<i>Used coexistence mechanisms (see respective experiment).</i>						
Storage Effect	-	No	Yes	Yes	-	No
Intransitivity	-	No	-	No	Yes	Yes
Resource Partitioning	-	No	-	No	-	No
<i>Information about the experimental setup.</i>						
Simulated Scenarios	11	11	11	11	5	5
Iterations per Scenario	100000	1000	100000	1000	1	1
Max. Simulated Generations	9999	9999	9999	9999	500	500